

PEDAGOGICAL SUPPORT FOR THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF FUTURE TEACHERS FOR TEACHING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

In order to characterize the capabilities of a university graduate, the degree of his adaptation to professional activities in a changing environment, the level of formation of the professional and pedagogical culture of students in the context of professionally oriented education was studied, which is determined by the following resources: personal predisposition to teaching, professional and pedagogical orientation, professional readiness, stability and awareness of the criteria of pedagogical activity. We can say that the professional training of specialists is understood as a set of properties and characteristics that determine the readiness of specialists for professional activities, including the ability to quickly adapt in the conditions of scientific and technological progress, possession of professional skills, knowledge, skills, and the ability to use them in solving professional problems. tasks.

The training of teaching staff is one of the most important conditions for stability, successful functioning and further development of both the education system and society as a whole. At present, the professional activity of teachers takes place in complex and contradictory conditions. One of the reasons for this is that there is a discrepancy, on the one hand, between the level of competence corresponding to the professional status of a teacher, demonstrated by the cultural level of a specialist, and, on the other hand, the real opportunities that are provided to achieve them. The society is faced with the task of creating a personnel pedagogical potential that is adequate in terms of its training to the level of professional culture and integrated into modern socio-economic conditions of life. A person's personality is formed under the influence of the language he speaks.

Language is not only a means of communication, a form of accumulation and transmission of information, but also acts as a tool for people to cognize material and spiritual reality. Among the "world" languages as a means of international communication, the role of the Russian language is exceptionally great. The Russian language is rightfully considered a world language, which is due to the entire course of the socio-political, economic, scientific,

technical and cultural development of mankind in the 20th – 21st centuries. Meanwhile, the lack of clear guidelines in the field of educational policy has a negative impact on the content of pedagogical activity. As a result, many teachers show passivity, unwillingness to change anything in their work, are biased towards objectively overdue innovations, which is largely due to the personal characteristics of teachers, such as low social professional activity, conservatism, indifference, which become an obstacle to reform education systems. In this regard, there is a need to determine the theoretical and methodological foundations of pedagogical support for the professional self-improvement of the future teacher. To date, a large theoretical and practical material has been accumulated that ensures the implementation of many aspects of the professional and pedagogical training of students, but a system of pedagogical support for their professional self-improvement has not been created, which necessitates additional research. At the same time, the analysis of scientific literature shows that there are certain prerequisites for the implementation of a theoretical understanding of this pedagogical phenomenon. However, the unresolved issues include questions about the goals of professional training in accordance with the changed paradigm of education in unity with its modernization, about the means of preparing for solving professional problems in dynamically changing conditions of professional activity, about approaches to creating systems that ensure the development of personally significant qualities of a teacher, about criteria for assessing the quality of professional and pedagogical training at the university. Many problems related to the search for effective means of forming a modern teacher who is ready for self-development and self-improvement continue to remain relevant, which requires adequate pedagogical support for the professional self-improvement of the future teacher. However, as the analysis of pedagogical practice shows, contradictions are revealed in education between: the increasing requirements for the personality of the teacher in connection with the modernization and reform of education and the discrepancy between professional and psychological characteristics of these requirements, the demand in the process of preparing means that provide a gradual stimulation of the future teacher for self-development and self-improvement and lack of conceptually substantiated systems of pedagogical support for these processes. The desire to find ways to resolve these contradictions determines the problem of our study. In theoretical terms, this is the problem of creating a system of pedagogical support for the professional self-improvement of a future teacher. In practical terms, this is the problem of determining the means of pedagogical support, the implementation of which ensures the formation of the readiness of the future teacher for professional self-improvement.

1. Methodological foundations of professionally oriented education of students of pedagogical universities

The process of modernization of the education system is accompanied by significant changes in the theory and practice of the educational process. There is a change in the educational paradigm, a different content of education is offered, traditional ways of presenting information give way to a different interaction between the teacher and the student. In the field of methodology of professionally oriented education and upbringing, there are scientific discussions and disputes affecting the sphere of technologies and innovations in education. New concepts are born, within the framework of which the changes

taking place in the views on the theory, methodology and technology of education are comprehended. But the indisputable fact remains that the educational process in a university should be, first of all, professionally oriented.

However, the organization of professionally oriented education in higher education is difficult due to the existing unresolved problems related, first of all, to its scientific and methodological support. At present, the professional activity of specialists in almost all areas is saturated with non-professional or over-professional components and the skills of interpreting and analyzing results, using a computer, databases and data banks, knowing a foreign language, etc., which should be attributed to general education. Therefore, the vocational school is increasingly taking over the functions of continuing the general education of young people. The moral imperative of any system of education is the requirement that the preparation of the individual correspond to the needs of developing social practice.

Methodology is a system of the most general principles that form the basis of a particular science. A set of methods used in any science, a set of basic principles and methods of scientific research.

Methodology (from the Greek μεθοδολογία - the doctrine of methods; from the ancient Greek μέθοδος from μετά- + ὁδός, lit. "the path following something" and the ancient Greek λόγος - thought, reason) - the doctrine of the methods, methods and strategies of research subject. In the works on teacher education, the theoretical and methodological foundations of professional training and education of the future teacher, its goals, values, content, etc. are quite fully disclosed. (A.A. Verbitsky, E.P. Belozertsev, N.V. Kuzmina, A.K. Markova, A.I. Mishchenko, L.I. Mishchenko, A.G. Pashkov, A.V. Reprintsev, V A. Slastenin, E.N. Shiyanov) and others. professional development of students and is a necessary condition for the successful professional activity of a specialist - a graduate of a modern higher school, able to make business contacts with foreign-language partners.

Theoretical and methodological basis are modern psychological and pedagogical theories of personality, activity, thinking; the main provisions of psychology, pedagogy about the individual as an active subject of activity; the concepts of personal and professional orientation in education, provisions on professional and pedagogical culture as a measure and method of creative self-realization of a teacher.

Thus, learning theory is traditionally regarded as a relatively independent part of pedagogical science. Modern didactics is designed to implement the ideas of humane pedagogy, aimed at the formation of a free, creative, socially active, useful and successful personality. Knowledge of the theory of learning is necessary for every teacher, since the tasks of education, upbringing and development of students in pedagogical activity are most effectively solved based on scientific knowledge.

The changes that have taken place all over the world, the increase in the role of science, the formation of an international scientific space, the expansion of international relations, the development of the media associated with the expansion of communication opportunities, as well as the transition to a personal paradigm as a higher degree of integrity in the cognition and design of educational processes, created the prerequisites for changing the situation in teaching foreign languages at a technical university. However, the emerging changes in teaching foreign languages at a technical university have not yet become the object of

methodological reflection and are reflected in most scientific works and in the mass pedagogical consciousness at the level of changes only in the content of language education.

This problem requires a comprehensive consideration, taking into account changes in the general scientific picture of the world. Considering the issues of methodological substantiation of the organization of the educational process in foreign languages in a non-linguistic university, we turn, first of all, to the problems that characterize it:

- 1) the lack of a developed scientific methodology for the functioning of the educational space of a non-linguistic university, corresponding to the modern general scientific picture of the world;
- 2) insufficient general level of motivation for learning among students, surveys and diagnostics show that only individual students are highly motivated;
- 3) the inertia of non-linguistic higher school teachers in introducing new information technologies into education, despite the high professional level, the habit of working with traditional methods;
- 4) insufficient development of the psychological and pedagogical foundations for organizing the educational process in a non-linguistic university, fundamental research on the pedagogy of a higher technical school is just beginning to appear;
- 5) insufficient level of information technology support of the educational process.

The solution of these problems is associated, first of all, with the formation of an innovative methodology for the functioning of the educational space of a technical university, including the development of new concepts, the search for new approaches and the best among the existing ones. Historical and pedagogical analysis of educational innovations testifies to the multiplicity of approaches to learning. A professionally oriented approach implies the formation of professional competence, which includes knowledge, skills and abilities in the specialty, and possession of professional terminology for the purpose of its further practical and theoretical use in professional activities. In accordance with the State Standard of Higher Professional Education of the Russian Federation, a modern specialist should not only have a high level of professional competence and be a comprehensively developed personality, but also be able to socially adapt to the needs of the time, replenish and practically apply his knowledge in changing conditions, take into account in his practical activities innovative technologies and the ever-increasing information field of the chosen specialty. Of particular importance in such conditions is the accumulation, expansion and replenishment of professional knowledge. This process occurs through communication with specialists or with sources of information. Professional communication is only possible.

An analysis of the existing concepts of education allows us to conclude that none of the concepts can be unambiguously attributed to one or another of the selected models and goes beyond the scope of this classification, since each of them is an integrated version that combines subject-didactic, socio-pedagogical and psychological aspects. This suggests that the theory of student-centered education is developing on the basis of an integral approach, i.e. integration of scientific knowledge about a person and his education. Modern education, based on the integration of various methods and sciences, contributes to a holistic understanding of the world and the growth of the creative potential of the individual: the co-evolution of man, nature and society determines the moral principles of harmonizing their

coexistence, and in the education environment - a departure from the subject differentiation of scientific knowledge as a means of effective learning and search for optimal ways of integrating knowledge. Differentiated ready-made knowledge forms reproductive thinking. Productive thinking is impossible without the use of creative efforts, therefore, an innovative approach to education involves the development of variable models of the educational process and course content, the fundamental principles of which will be the integration and creative development of the individual. The processes of knowledge integration can be traced in the interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary concepts of education, but these concepts are still waiting for their implementers, since they require, first of all, teachers to see the general axiomatics of all disciplines at various levels, the unity of their inner essence with its most diverse external manifestations. The specificity of the integral approach as a methodology of interdisciplinary knowledge lies in the dominance of integrative, synthesizing trends in learning. This approach contributes to the restoration of holistic ideas about the world, the picture of the world as a single process. The integration of knowledge based on interdisciplinary connections makes it possible to provide a holistic vision of any problems, situations, phenomena in the fullness of versatility and multidimensionality at a new, higher level. 1. The problem of teaching Russian as a foreign language in a pedagogical university

The problem of professionally oriented education requires special and constant consideration, and each new generation of students of future teachers forces a new approach to its solution.

In this regard, the learning process in a pedagogical university requires such an organization in which the student would become the subject of educational activity. With this approach, special attention is paid to the development of the student's individuality (V.A. Artemov, V.B. Barbe, N.A. Bakholskaya, B.V. Belyaev, V.V. Grachev, K.M. Gurevich, I.A. Zimnyaya, A.G. Kovalev, A.A. Leontiev, N.E. Mazhar, R.Kh. Swassing). Researches of a number of scientists (E.P. Belozertsev, B.JI. Benin, E.V. Bondarevskaya, N.I. Vyunova, I.F. Isaev V.A. Kan-Kalik, L.I. Mishchenko, P.I. Obratsov, L.S. Podymova, V.A. Slastenin, A.I. Uman, A.N. Khodusov, E.N. Shiyonov, etc.) it is proved that among the qualities of a teacher are general professional, methodical, subject, the first (general professional) are of particular importance. At the same time, the ability for creative activity and the presence of a high level of pedagogical culture are important components of the teacher's professional activity.

Pedagogical activity is inextricably linked with the desire for self-education, self-education, communicative activity, which are important characteristics of professionally oriented education (V.V. Kraevsky, A.N. Leontiev, V.A. Kan-Kalik, V.I. Zagvyazinsky and others .) Therefore, their formation should be given special attention in the targeted training of teachers in the classroom in a foreign language (E.I. Passov, E.K. Damzova, I.B. Ignatova, O.I. Medvedeva, I.E. Belogortseva and others .)

The issues of teaching a foreign language in higher educational institutions, its role and place in professional training were considered by A.A. Mirolyubov, A.V. Parkhina, S.A. Tylkina, M.D. Rybakov and others.

Thus, despite the urgent need to train teachers with a high level of professional pedagogical culture, with pronounced creative inclinations, capable of introspection, developing and realizing the possibilities of their professional potential, the problem of

organizing professionally oriented education has not yet found sufficient reflection in pedagogical science. which, in turn, reduces the quality of professional training of future teachers.”

As the analysis of various scientific and pedagogical sources shows, the problem of pedagogical conditions that ensure the professionally oriented activity of the future teacher in the system of forming his professional and pedagogical culture is the least developed. The process of globalization implies the need for representatives of different peoples to actively learn about each other. Direct acquaintance with other cultures is carried out primarily through language. The developing economic relations between Russia and other countries and the resulting need for a high level of Russian language proficiency place special demands on the methods used for teaching Russian as a foreign language (RFL). However, we have to state the fact that the level of training of students of the Russian language remains unsatisfactory. This is partly due to the fact that some issues of the theory and practice of creating nationally-oriented textbooks on Russian as a foreign language in terms of learning in a non-linguistic environment have not been sufficiently studied, there are no new forms of motivation for learning the Russian language, etc.

Conclusion

The conducted research allowed us to conclude that the professional training of specialists is understood as a set of properties and characteristics that determine the readiness of specialists for professional activities, including the ability to quickly adapt in the conditions of scientific and technological progress, possession of professional skills, knowledge, skills, and the ability to use them. when solving professional problems. Modern society has realized the need to train graduates of a pedagogical university with a high level of development of professional and pedagogical culture and a rich spiritual world. But here it is necessary to pay attention to the study of the external (in relation to the student) system of relations, and internal (the individual's own consciousness), since the comparison of "external" and "internal" values gives meaning to a person's existence, which leads us to the search for a new approach to professional development. -oriented learning. In order to characterize the capabilities of a university graduate, the degree of his adaptation to professional activities in a changing environment, we studied the level of formation of students' professional and pedagogical culture in the context of professionally oriented education, which is determined by the following resources: personal predisposition to teaching, professional and pedagogical orientation, professional preparedness, stability and awareness of the criteria of pedagogical activity. The most significant qualities of a professional, in our opinion, are: professional self-respect, professional creativity, professionally oriented orientation, a high level of professional and pedagogical culture, flexibility of professional behavior, professional value orientations and competence in time. The material presented in the abstract does not exhaust all aspects of the considered complex and multifaceted problem. It seems interesting to consider the problem in several relevant areas: the study of the formation of a system of continuous training of specialists at all stages and levels of professionally oriented education in the Russian language; identifying the conditions for dynamic stability of the structure of the space of activity and its actual implementation in a rapidly changing professional environment; development, optimization

and widespread use of technology for the development of a professional environment in distance forms of education in the Russian language.

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